

ISic0378

Funerary inscription for Tyche

Language

Type

Material

Object

Editor

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Autopsy

2017.03.20

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Catina

Place of origin (modern)

Catania

Provenance

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Catania, Museo Civico di
Catania, inventory 393

Physical Description

A square plaque of white marble, intact on all four sides, finished smooth on the reverse.

Dimensions

Height 25 cm
Width 30.5 cm
Depth 2.3 cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Lines 1-3: 13-18 mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: Not measured mm

Text

1. D (is) · M (anibus) · s (acrum)
2. Tyche vixit annis
3. XIII · men (sibus) · III · dieb (us) · XXI ·
4. parentes fecerunt

Apparatus

Translation (en)

Sacred to the spirits of the underworld. Tyche lived for 14 years, 3 months, 21 days. Her parents made this.

Translation (it)

Sacro agli Dei Mani. Tyche visse 14 anni, 3 mesi, 21 giorni. I suoi genitori lo

costruirono.

Commentary

The name Tyche is a Greek name meaning '(good) fortune'. The act of funerary commemoration in an epitaph reflects the values of society: Tyche was approaching the typical age at which young women would be likely to get married (late teens), and so the decision to erect an epitaph makes clear not only the grief but the disappointed hopes of the parents - the precision of age, which may or may not be genuine, serves to emphasise the loss.

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Bibliography

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